

1 Soil health is associated with higher primary productivity across
2 Europe

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31 Abstract

32 Soil health is expected to be of key importance for plant growth and ecosystem functioning.
33 However, whether soil health is linked to primary productivity across environmental gradients
34 and land-use types remains poorly understood. To address this gap, we conducted a pan-
35 European field study including 588 sites from 27 countries to investigate the link between soil
36 health and primary productivity across three major land-use types: woodlands, grasslands, and
37 croplands. We found that mean soil health (a composite index based on soil properties,
38 biodiversity, and plant disease control) in woodlands was 31.4% higher than in grasslands and
39 76.1% higher than in croplands. Soil health was positively linked to cropland and grassland
40 productivity at the continental scale, while climate best explained woodland productivity.
41 Among microbial diversity indicators, we observed a positive association between the richness
42 of Acidobacteria, Firmicutes, and Proteobacteria and primary productivity. Among microbial
43 functional groups, we found that primary productivity in croplands and grasslands was positively
44 related to nitrogen-fixing bacteria and mycorrhizal fungi, and negatively related to plant
45 pathogens. Together, our results point to the importance of soil biodiversity and soil health for
46 maintaining primary productivity across contrasting land-use types.

47 Introduction

48 Soil health refers to the capacity of soils to continuously support plant productivity and other
49 ecosystem functions, such as nutrient cycling, water filtration, and climate regulation ^{1,2}. This
50 encompasses the interplay of soil biotic and abiotic components, such as organic carbon content
51 and nutrient availability, alongside the diversity of soil organisms ^{1,3}. For example, despite being
52 overlooked in the past, there is growing consensus on the importance of soil microbial diversity
53 for soil and human health ⁴. In line with this, healthier soils usually exhibit higher organic carbon
54 content but also a higher diversity of beneficial microorganisms such as mycorrhizal fungi and
55 rhizobia, and lower richness of pathogens ⁵⁻⁷.

56 Functions provided by healthy soils and attributable to soil biodiversity include enhanced
57 nutrient acquisition by plants, improved soil structure, soil carbon storage, water retention
58 capacity, and disease control ^{1,8-10}. Despite the growing interest in soil health and how it
59 contributes to plant productivity in the European Union political agenda ¹¹, evidence across large
60 environmental and management scenarios is still missing ^{1,12}. For example, the relationship
61 between soil health and productivity may vary between natural or semi-natural ecosystems like
62 grasslands and forests, and managed ecosystems like croplands, with the latter frequently
63 influenced by agricultural practices.

64 The link between soil health and plant productivity across different land-use types might differ
65 due to variations in biological, physical, and chemical soil properties. Mature woodlands, for
66 example, are stable ecosystems without large-scale soil disturbance (e.g., regular tillage) and are
67 thought to display high levels of soil health. Woodlands are also dominated by trees with deep
68 root systems that can access nutrients from deeper soil layers and can store them in their
69 biomass for decades ¹³. Additionally, the slow decomposition of leaf litter in woodlands
70 contributes to soil organic matter and nutrient availability over time, which may lead to a
71 gradual increase in primary productivity as the forest matures ¹⁴. Consequently, as it is already
72 high, soil health may be less important for productivity in woodlands, and other factors (e.g.,
73 water availability and temperature) may have a bigger impact on woodland productivity. On the
74 other hand, grasslands and croplands represent a more “ruderal” dynamic and disturbed state
75 and are often characterized by dense and short root networks of grasses and forbs that grow
76 and die seasonally, leading to a rapid turnover of nutrients and organic matter ^{15,16}. Pathogens
77 are also relatively more abundant in these ecosystems ¹⁷, and nutrients are more easily leached
78 out ^{18,19}. Consequently, such ecosystems might be more reliant on soil health to regulate
79 productivity.

80 Certain microbial groups are particularly beneficial for primary productivity, such as plant-
81 growth promoting rhizobacteria, and mycorrhizal fungi^{20,21}. Such functional groups of microbes
82 are important for soil health^{22,23}. However, the question of whether productivity is similarly
83 driven by biological components of soil health (i.e., microbial diversity) across contrasting land-
84 use types remains unexplored, as a systematic large-scale comparison among different land-
85 uses is lacking and large-scale monitoring efforts are scarce^{24,25}.

86 Here, we tested whether soil health is positively linked to primary productivity across Europe. In
87 addition, we tested which soil variables best explained primary productivity. Our analysis is
88 based on 588 sites from 27 countries, and we assessed three major land-use types in Europe:
89 woodlands (n = 185), grasslands (n = 126), and croplands (n = 277). As a measure of soil health,
90 we used a composite index built from seven soil properties including abiotic and biotic factors
91 (i.e., soil organic carbon, phosphorus content, water infiltration potential, microbial biomass,
92 the richness of N-fixing bacteria, the richness of mycorrhizal -arbuscular and ectomycorrhizal-
93 fungi, and plant disease control - see methods). As a measure of primary productivity, we used
94 the Fraction of Absorbed Photosynthetically Active Radiation (FAPAR) derived from remote
95 sensing data obtained from each of the 588 sampling locations. Specifically, we tested whether
96 the relationship between soil health and productivity differs among contrasting land-use types.
97 We hypothesized that less disturbed ecosystems (i.e., woodlands) would show healthier soils
98 compared to grasslands and croplands. We also hypothesized that soil health would affect
99 primary productivity in grasslands and croplands more immediately than in woodlands.

100 Results and discussion

101 Here we assessed the link between soil health and primary productivity, examining 588 sites
102 across three land-use types (i.e., croplands, grasslands, and woodlands) in Europe (Figure 1). We
103 found the highest soil health values in woodlands compared to grasslands and croplands.
104 According to our initial hypothesis, soil health in woodlands was ~31% higher than in grasslands,
105 and ~76% higher than in croplands (Figure 2). Soil health was positively linked to primary
106 productivity when all sites were taken together (Figure 2). In line with our expectations, soil
107 health was positively linked to primary productivity in grasslands and croplands, but not in
108 woodlands (Figure 2). We also found that soil health was more related with primary productivity
109 in croplands and grasslands than any of the individual variables used to compute the index.
110 Specifically, the correlation between soil health and productivity was 3.17 times higher than the
111 average of individual variables for croplands, and 2.64 times higher for grasslands (Table S3).
112 Our soil health index encapsulated a range of abiotic and biotic soil factors, thus providing a
113 comprehensive metric that is comparable across land-use types and that can inform policy,
114 farmers, and land managers.

115 Next, we assessed which individual variables best explained primary productivity. Overall, our
116 results demonstrate that a combination of climatic and edaphic factors, together with soil
117 biodiversity, explains patterns in primary productivity across contrasting land-use types at the
118 European scale: our structural equation models explained 40% of the variability in primary
119 productivity in grasslands, 35% in woodlands, and 31% in croplands (Figures 3 and 4). Our results
120 demonstrate that spatial variations in cropland and grassland productivity are best explained by
121 various factors of soil health, including edaphic properties (e.g., organic carbon) and soil
122 microbial diversity. In woodlands, our results imply that temperature is a major regulator of
123 primary productivity, although specific components of soil health (e.g., phosphorus content,
124 organic matter, and the richness of Actinobacteria and Proteobacteria) also do play a role.
125 Moreover, we observed that various components of microbial diversity act as relevant
126 predictors of primary productivity, including the richness of Acidobacteria, Firmicutes,
127 Proteobacteria, and mycorrhizal fungi (Figure 3, Figure 4).

128 Overall, our results indicate a positive relationship between soil health and cropland productivity
129 (Figure 2). Random Forest analyses further indicated that pH was the main predictor of primary
130 productivity in croplands. This confirms previous evidence on the role of pH in driving crop
131 productivity²⁶. Accordingly, we observed the lowest cropland productivity in highly alkaline (pH
132 ≈ 8) soils (Figure S1). Other edaphic factors showed positive effects on cropland productivity,

133 namely soil organic carbon and phosphorus content (Figure 3, Figure S1). Among climatic
134 factors, we observed a negative effect of increasing temperature on cropland productivity, while
135 the effect of increasing precipitation was positive (Figure 3, Figure S1). Our study also included
136 Mediterranean locations (which are very dry in summer), and as such this observation does not
137 come as a surprise as water availability is a key regulator of plant productivity. Our results further
138 indicate that microbial community composition was the best microbial predictor of cropland
139 productivity (Figure S2). In line with this, random forest analyses on cropland sites also indicated
140 that specific microbial groups predicted cropland productivity: that was the case for
141 Acidobacteria, Firmicutes, and Proteobacteria. The richness of these bacterial groups was
142 positively correlated with productivity, while a negative effect was observed for Actinobacteria
143 (Figure 3, Figure S3).

144 Structural equation models (SEMs) further demonstrated that edaphic factors (e.g., soil texture,
145 soil organic carbon, pH, phosphorus content) affected cropland productivity also indirectly by
146 leading to changes on the diversity of soil microorganisms, particularly the bacterial taxa
147 Acidobacteria and Firmicutes, and the fungal phylum Chytridiomycota (Figure 4). Structural
148 equation models confirmed a positive direct effect of increased richness of Acidobacteria and
149 Firmicutes on cropland productivity, while the opposite was observed for Chytridiomycota (i.e.,
150 increased OTU richness led to lower productivity). Acidobacteria are abundant soil-borne
151 microorganisms known to be involved in nutrient mineralization and organic matter
152 degradation²⁷⁻²⁹. Our results also align with a recent study where Acidobacteria positively
153 correlated with cropland productivity in a four-decade fertilization experiment³⁰. Similarly,
154 members of the phylum Firmicutes, known for their widespread presence in soils and for
155 promoting plant growth locally, appear to also enhance cropland productivity on a continental
156 scale^{31,32}. Finally, SEMs indicated that the richness of Chytridiomycota was negatively related to
157 cropland productivity (Figure 4). While this fungal group is best known for parasitizing
158 vertebrates, some species are responsible for plant disease in Europe³³. In line with this, we
159 observed a negative correlation between the richness of fungal plant pathogens and cropland
160 productivity (Figure S3).

161 The grasslands included in this study were, on average, slightly more acidic than croplands and
162 showed higher microbial biomass and higher organic carbon content, but lower phosphorus
163 content when compared (see full details in Table S4). Bacterial richness was lower in grasslands
164 compared to croplands, but fungal richness was slightly higher (Table S4). As for croplands, our
165 results indicate a positive relationship between soil health and grassland productivity (Figure 2).

166 Random forest analyses retained four factors as predictors of primary productivity in grasslands,
167 namely pH, soil organic carbon, and the richness of Proteobacteria and mycorrhizal fungi (Figure
168 3). Similar to croplands, pH showed a hump-shaped to negative response, with productivity
169 peaking at $\text{pH} \approx 6$. The relationship between grassland productivity and soil organic carbon,
170 Proteobacteria, and mycorrhizal fungi was positive. Grasslands represent large carbon sinks, and
171 most of it is stored belowground as soil organic carbon³⁴. Recent studies show that plant
172 diversity increases soil organic carbon storage in grasslands by elevating carbon inputs to
173 belowground biomass and promoting microbial necromass contribution to soil organic carbon
174 storage^{35,36}. Our results add to this and show that soil organic carbon is positively linked to plant
175 productivity for grasslands at the continental scale, indicating that soil organic carbon favors
176 carbon storage, but also has positive effects on productivity. Although we did not differentiate
177 between necromass and living biomass in our study, we also found positive correlations
178 between bacterial richness/ microbial biomass and grassland productivity (Figure S1, Figure S2).
179 Structural equation models further supported the idea that grassland productivity was
180 determined by pH and soil organic carbon (Figure 4). Moreover, SEMs indicated a direct positive
181 effect of Proteobacteria richness on grassland productivity, and a negative direct effect of
182 Chytridiomycota.

183 Finally, woodlands showed the lowest pH and phosphorus content compared to croplands and
184 grasslands, but the highest organic carbon content. Woodlands also showed the lowest values
185 of bacterial and fungal richness (see full details in Table S4). Random forest modelling of the 185
186 woodland sites included in this study revealed that the best predictors of woodland productivity
187 were monthly temperature, clay content, soil organic carbon, bulk density, richness of
188 Firmicutes, microbial biomass, and monthly precipitation (Figure 3). Only bulk density showed a
189 negative effect on woodland productivity, all other predictors were positively associated to it.
190 SEMs revealed that woodland productivity was shaped by a complex interplay between climatic
191 factors (i.e., temperature), edaphic factors (i.e., clay content, soil organic carbon, and
192 phosphorus content) and soil biodiversity (richness of Actinobacteria and Proteobacteria).
193 Specifically, SEMs depicted a strong positive effect of temperature on woodland productivity,
194 although factors associated to soil diversity (e.g., richness of Actinobacteria and Proteobacteria)
195 also shaped woodland productivity (Figure 4). Recent studies suggest that fungal communities
196 are major drivers of ecosystem functioning in woodlands^{37,38}. Our SEM adds to this that fungal
197 communities (particularly plant-beneficial members within Mortierellomycota, Basidiomycota,
198 and mycorrhizal fungi) in woodlands are shaped by a combination of climatic factors (i.e.,
199 precipitation) and edaphic properties. Importantly, we also show that future studies addressing

200 the impacts of the soil microbiome on woodland productivity need to include bacteria. This is
201 because major bacterial divisions (i.e., Actinobacteria and Proteobacteria) were closely related
202 to primary productivity in the woodlands included in our study.

203 In our study, primary productivity was significantly lower in croplands, compared to grasslands
204 and woodlands, following previous research³⁹ (Figure S4). In line with our hypothesis, primary
205 productivity relied more strongly on soil health in grasslands and croplands than in woodlands.
206 Woodland productivity was largely governed by temperature, in line with previous findings^{40,41}.
207 Moreover, we observed the highest soil health values in woodlands. We argue that above a
208 tipping point of soil health, other factors (i.e., climate), might become more important when it
209 comes to explaining primary productivity. Finally, agricultural crops often have a short lifespan,
210 rely on a fast delivery of nutrients and might be more dependent on soil health compared to less
211 dynamic and more stable ecosystems like woodlands. In line with this, a recent study assessed
212 soil health and crop productivity in 60 fields managed either conventionally, under no-till, or
213 organically⁴². That study found that the management type with the lowest soil health,
214 conventionally managed croplands, relied most on soil health when it comes to explaining plant
215 productivity. Similarly, a recent greenhouse experiment showed that soil health is positively
216 linked to nitrogen use efficiency⁸. This indicates that soil health is especially important as driver
217 of plant productivity and other ecosystem processes in disturbed agricultural soils. Among the
218 different soil properties here assessed, we found strong correlations between total nitrogen and
219 phosphorus and plant productivity across land-use types. We highlight that future studies should
220 focus on their inorganic mineral forms, as these are more readily available to plants in soil. This
221 aspect was not addressed in our study due to the high number of samples involved.

222 We here addressed whether soil health associates with primary productivity at the continental
223 scale through a comprehensive soil health index that encapsulates a broad spectrum of soil
224 properties. However, we recognize the inherent challenge of capturing the complexity of
225 contrasting soil systems into a single metric, particularly in large-scale assessments where the
226 number of available variables may be limited. Here, we found significant correlations between
227 soil health and primary productivity, emphasizing the link between soil health and ecosystem
228 functioning. Future research should investigate the relationships between soil health and other
229 ecosystem functions, notably climate regulation, to comprehensively understand the impact of
230 soil health on ecosystem dynamics. Importantly, our study mostly relies on observational data,
231 necessitating further experimental validation to establish causal relationships. Experimental
232 manipulation of soil health variables identified here as potential drivers of primary productivity,

233 such as soil organic carbon and microbial diversity, is crucial ^{43,44}. In line with this, previous
234 laboratory-based studies have suggested that richness of arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi promotes
235 plant productivity ^{45,46}, but field experiments are needed to confirm these findings. For instance,
236 recent research introduced mycorrhizal fungi to croplands and found both positive and negative
237 effects on primary productivity ⁴⁷. In order to elucidate its impact on productivity in different
238 contexts, future studies should include a gradient of fungal richness. Finally, we highlight the
239 need to complement our NDVI-based vegetation analysis with other remote sensing methods
240 such as light detection and ranging (LIDAR), as well as with actual plant biomass measurements,
241 although we recognize the considerable technical challenges associated with conducting such
242 detailed biomass studies at large scales.

243 In summary, our results provide compelling evidence in support of the hypothesis that primary
244 productivity is linked to soil health at the continental scale, particularly for grasslands and
245 croplands. Among the soil health indicators assessed here, we highlight the positive effects of
246 soil organic carbon and the richness of Acidobacteria, Firmicutes, and Proteobacteria on primary
247 productivity. In contrast, the richness of Actinobacteria and major plant pathogens including
248 Chytridiomycota was negatively related to primary productivity. Our study points to the
249 importance of soil health as a driver of primary productivity and it highlights the need to include
250 microorganisms in soil monitoring schemes to gain a comprehensive understanding of
251 ecosystem functioning in terrestrial ecosystems.

252 Methods

253 *Field survey and soil sampling*

254 This study was carried out within the EU Statistical Office's Land Use and Coverage Area frame
255 Survey (LUCAS), the largest pan-European scheme for assessing soil characteristics in relation to
256 land cover and use ⁴⁸. As part of the 2018 LUCAS Soil survey, 881 fresh soil samples were
257 collected across Europe and stored at -20°C before further processing ⁴⁹. The sampling followed
258 a composite strategy: the final sample collected at each location comprised five topsoil (0-20
259 cm) subsamples that were physically mixed to form a single composite sample. The first
260 subsample was taken at the precise GIS (geographical information system) coordinates of the
261 pre-established LUCAS point, and the remaining four subsamples were taken 2 m from the
262 central one following the cardinal directions (North, East, South, and West). For this study, we
263 focused on 277 cropland, 126 grassland, and 185 woodland sites across 27 countries (Figure 1).
264 The most common crops included common wheat (62 sites), barley (39 sites), and maize (29
265 sites), alongside others like olive groves (20 sites) and rapeseed (15 sites). Most of the grasslands
266 included in this study were extensive (112 sites), with 92 completely lacking tree or shrub cover,
267 and 20 showing sparse tree/shrub cover. Woodlands included mostly broadleaved (71 sites) and
268 coniferous (55 sites) forests. Sampling lasted from May to December 2018. The selection was
269 based on the availability of all critical variables (soil biodiversity, edaphic factors, and primary
270 productivity).

271 *Soil microbial diversity*

272 Soil DNA was extracted from each of the 588 composite soil samples using the Qiagen DNeasy
273 PowerSoil HTP 96 Kit Q12955-4. Three 0.2 g aliquots per sample were extracted and pooled.
274 Negative and positive controls were included to determine the presence of any external
275 contamination. DNA extracts were quantified and checked for quality using a QubitTM 1X dsDNA
276 HS Assay Kit and a QubitTM 3 Fluorometer (Invitrogen). Primer sets for barcode amplification
277 were 515F (GTGYCAGCMGCCGCGGTAA) and 926R (GGCCGYCAATTYMTTTRAGTTT) for the
278 bacterial 16S region ^{50,51}, and ITS9mun (GTACACACCGCCCGTCG) and ITS4ngsUni
279 (CGCCTSCCTTANTDATATGC) for the fungal ITS region ⁵². Sequencing was performed by Illumina
280 MiSeq platform with 2 x 300 paired-end mode for bacterial amplicons and PacBio Sequel II
281 platform for fungal amplicons ¹⁷.

282 The Illumina and PacBio amplicon data (for bacteria and fungi, respectively) were demultiplexed
283 using LotuS2 (v2.23)⁵³, and paired-end reads were assembled setting a minimum overlap of 10
284 bp using FLASH 1.2.10⁵⁴. Reads failing to merge were removed from the final dataset. For
285 bacteria, operational taxonomic units (OTUs) were generated with the *usearch* option (version
286 10.0.024) available in UPARSE⁵⁵. Merged reads were truncated up to the 16S primer sequences
287 (i.e., 515F and 926R) and filtered for the presence of primer sequences (allowing a maximum of
288 2 mismatches). Merged reads were further quality-filtered with *usearch* by removing sequences
289 with more than one expected error, and duplicated sequences were collapsed with *fqtrim*
290 version 0.9.7⁵⁶. Obtained OTUs were annotated with the taxonomy data available from the
291 Ribosomal Database Project⁵⁷. To avoid sequencing artifacts, only OTUs with at least 50 read
292 counts and present in at least 10 samples were kept. For fungi, 98%-OTUs were used⁵⁸. Fungal
293 taxonomic annotation was performed using BLAST+ version 2.11.0⁵⁹ against the UNITE 9.1
294 database⁶⁰. Bacterial and fungal datasets were further rarefied to comparable sequencing
295 depths (bacteria: 40,109 reads; fungi: 502 reads). Rarefied datasets were used to obtain values
296 of total richness (i.e., OTU number), community composition (extracted values from the first
297 dimension of NMDS based on Bray-Curtis dissimilarities), and the richness of major microbial
298 groups (i.e., phyla). Rarefied datasets were also used to obtain the richness of major functional
299 groups as retrieved from the FAPROTAX (bacteria) and FungalTraits (fungi) databases^{61,62} (Table
300 S1). Briefly, we retrieved the number of OTUs classified as bacterial chemoheterotrophs,
301 nitrogen-fixing bacteria, fungal saprotrophs, fungal plant pathogens, and mycorrhizal fungi⁶³.

302 *Edaphic and climatic factors*

303 The following measurements were taken for each sampling site to ensure a comprehensive
304 understanding of climatic and edaphic factors⁶⁴: Total nitrogen and phosphorus content were
305 assessed to determine nutrient pools in the soil. Soil organic carbon was quantified to estimate
306 the amount of carbon stored in the soil organic matter during sampling. Soil pH and microbial
307 biomass were used as measures of acidity and activity of the living component of the soil,
308 respectively. Soil bulk density was used as a surrogate of water infiltration potential. Soil texture
309 was characterized by measuring silt, sand, and clay relative content. Additionally, to capture the
310 broader climatic context of each site, mean annual precipitation and mean annual temperature
311 (i.e., averaged monthly values over a long period of time; 1970-2000) were retrieved from the
312 WorldClim database (www.worldclim.org). These parameters collectively provided a detailed
313 profile of the environmental and soil conditions at each sampling site (Table S1).

314 *Primary productivity*

315 The Net Primary Productivity (NPP) was derived from images taken by the NASA Terra and Aqua
316 satellites using their MODerate resolution Imaging Spectroradiometers (MODIS). The NPP is
317 calculated as the sum of the MODIS eight-days Net Photosynthesis (PSN) products. PSN is in turn
318 estimated from the Fraction of Absorbed Photosynthetically Active Radiation (FAPAR), which is
319 the fraction of the incoming solar radiation (in the photosynthetically active spectrum) absorbed
320 by plants. FAPAR is closely related to NDVI (normalized difference vegetation index), that has
321 been used as a proxy for plant biomass in several studies relating soil biodiversity and primary
322 productivity^{63,66,67}. However, the derivation of PSN from FAPAR, provides a more reliable
323 estimate of the NPP as it accounts for the ground conditions in which the photosynthesis occurs
324 and for the plant maintenance respiration. Thus, this computation requires additional
325 information such as the maximum radiation conversion efficiency, the ground temperature, and
326 vapour pressure. The calculation is performed following the MOD17 PSN/NPP algorithm⁶⁸. For
327 this study the NPP was derived from MODIS products for year 2018 (to match with the LUCAS
328 survey) at a resolution of 500 m^{64,69}. The NPP values were derived for the months before, during,
329 and after sampling at each LUCAS location and subsequently averaged.

330 *Soil health*

331 In this study, we used seven explanatory variables, namely soil organic carbon, phosphorus
332 content, water infiltration potential, microbial biomass, richness of N-fixing bacteria, richness of
333 mycorrhizal (arbuscular and ectomycorrhizal) fungi, and plant disease control to build a soil
334 health index¹ (Table S2). These variables were selected as they collectively represent a broad
335 range of soil characteristics that are critical for understanding soil health-productivity
336 relationships. Soil organic carbon is crucial for nutrient cycling and soil structure; phosphorus
337 content is a key nutrient for plant growth; water infiltration potential influences water
338 availability and root development; microbial biomass indicates the biological activity essential
339 for nutrient transformation; richness of N-fixing bacteria and mycorrhizal fungi reflects soil
340 capacity for nitrogen fixation and nutrient uptake, respectively; and plant disease control
341 highlights the role of soil in supporting plant health. Plant disease control was here calculated
342 using the FungalTraits database to categorize fungal taxa into functional groups (i.e., mycorrhiza,
343 pathogens). Fungal taxa selected as plant pathogens were carefully screened to prevent mis-
344 categorizations. For each sampling location, plant disease control was computed as the inverse
345 of the total richness of potential fungal pathogens, following the procedure described in
346 previous studies^{70,71}. Finally, the soil health index was calculated using z-score transformation:
347 each variable was standardized to have a mean of 0 and a standard deviation of 1. The soil health

348 index for each site was then computed by summing its respective z-scores (i.e., equally
349 weighting). This approach allowed us to integrate multiple soil health indicators into a single
350 composite index, facilitating a comprehensive assessment.

351 *Statistics*

352 Statistical analyses were performed using R software, version 4.2.1. Only soil samples for which
353 all explanatory variables (i.e., soil biodiversity and climatic, edaphic, and spatial factors) were
354 available were used for this study, so none of the values in any explanatory variables was
355 imputed or calculated from the median value of the respective dataset. The raw data (DNA
356 sequences) used in this study can be found in the Sequence Read Archive (SRA) database under
357 BioProject ID PRJNA952168. A dataset including detailed information on each individual
358 sampling site used in this study (n = 588) is available at
359 <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.26272657> (see also Supplementary Dataset). R scripts
360 designed for data analyses and figure production are available at
361 <https://github.com/fromerob/Romero-et-al-2024-Soil-Health.git>. A total of 588 sites were used
362 for this study, including 277 croplands, 126 grasslands, and 185 woodlands (Figure 1). To assess
363 the most important predictors of primary productivity within the three land-use systems, we
364 used Random Forest⁷² followed by structural equation modeling⁷³.

365 First, we selected a wide range of explanatory variables including biodiversity indicators (i.e.,
366 OTU richness, diversity, community composition), together with climatic and edaphic factors.
367 The total number of explanatory variables was 34 (Table S1). We then investigated the
368 correlation among all variables to ensure that there was no strong collinearity and reduced the
369 variables that were strongly correlated (i.e., Spearman rank correlation coefficient higher than
370 +0.70, or lower than -0.70). Correlations were run using the *corr* function within the *corrplot*
371 package⁷⁴. This approach reduced the 34 explanatory variables to 24 (croplands), 23
372 (grasslands), and 19 (woodlands) (Table S1). The variables removed included alpha and beta
373 diversity indices (strong correlation with specific microbial groups, e.g., Proteobacteria), total
374 nitrogen (strong correlation with soil organic carbon), richness of chemoheterotrophic bacteria
375 (strong correlation with Actinobacteria and total bacteria), and silt and sand content (strong
376 correlation with clay content).

377 To further clarify the relative contribution of climate, edaphic factors, and soil biodiversity to
378 explain patterns in primary productivity, we conducted random forest analyses. The random
379 forest analyses were performed independently for the three land-use types using 10,000

380 permutations. Random forest analyses were performed using the *rfPermute* package ⁷⁵.
381 Predictor importance was estimated by the percent increase in Mean Squared Error (MSE) when
382 each predictor was permuted. This reflects the contribution of each predictor to model accuracy;
383 a higher increase in MSE indicates greater importance for accurate predictions. Finally, we
384 employed Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) to evaluate the direct and indirect relationships
385 between climate, edaphic factors, soil biodiversity, and primary productivity. We used the R
386 package *piecewiseR* for SEM ⁷⁶.

387 Data availability

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389 (SRA) database under BioProject ID PRJNA952168. A dataset including detailed information on
390 each individual sampling site used in this study (n = 588) is available at
391 <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.26272657>

392 Code availability

393 R scripts designed for data analyses and figure production are available at
394 <https://github.com/fromerob/Romero-et-al-2024-Soil-Health.git>

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412 Author Contributions Statement

413 F.R., MvdH, M.L., and A.O. conceptualized and designed the study. M.L., L.T., M.B. generated or
414 processed the sequencing data. F.R., M.L., D.T., and C.B., conducted statistical analyses
415 (investigation, visualization). C.B. calculated primary productivity values for each site. A.O., P.P.,
416 A.J., coordinated the sampling campaign. MvdH, A.O., P.P., and A.J. handled project
417 administration. F.R. and MvdH wrote original draft. The following authors contributed to
418 reviewing and editing: F.R., M.L., A.O., C.B., P.P., A.J., L.T., M.B., C.A.G., N.E., D.T., M.D.B., P.G.P.,
419 MvdH.

420 Competing Interests Statement

421 The authors declare no competing interests.

422 Figure Legends/Captions

423 **Figure 1.** Geographic distribution across the European continent of the 588 locations used
424 in this study. Three major land-use types were covered in the survey: woodlands (n = 185,
425 purple), grasslands (n = 126, green), and croplands (n = 277, yellow).

426 **Figure 2.** Relationship between soil health and primary productivity. **A**, Soil health index
427 across land-use types: woodlands (W, n = 185), grasslands (G, n = 126), and croplands
428 (C, n = 277). Grouping information (letters above boxplots) is provided as pairwise
429 comparisons following Kruskal-Wallis (two-sided) rank test (different letters indicate
430 significant difference at $p < 0.05$). Chi-squared (χ^2) provides an estimation of the overall
431 difference among land use types, and degrees of freedom are indicated as "d.f". Boxplots
432 indicate median (middle line), 25th and 75th percentiles (box), minimum, and maximum
433 (whiskers). Boxplots also indicate outlier values. **B**, relationship between the soil health
434 index and primary productivity. Explained variation is expressed as R^2 (0-1). Non-significant
435 (p -value > 0.05) regressions are denoted with "n.s.".

436 **Figure 3.** Relative importance of main predictors (top-10) for primary productivity based on
437 random forest analysis in croplands (**A**, n = 277), grasslands (**B**, n = 126) and woodlands
438 (**C**, n = 185). Dark colors indicate positive predictor effects on primary productivity, and light

439 colors indicate negative effects. Variance explained by models is indicated as percentage
440 (%). Asterisks indicate a significant effect based on averaged model coefficients following
441 permutation testing with 1000 permutations (***; p-value < 0.001, **; p-value < 0.010, *; p-
442 value < 0.050). Exact p-values for each predictor are available in Supplementary Table S5.

443 **Figure 4.** Structural equation modeling (SEM) describing direct and indirect effects of
444 climate, edaphic factors, and soil biodiversity on primary productivity across different land-
445 use types. The proportion of explained variance (R^2) in primary productivity is indicated for
446 each model. Goodness-of-fit statistics are also included. Dashed lines indicate that none
447 of the variables included was significant (p -value > 0.05). d.f.: degrees of freedom, AIC:
448 Akaike information criterion. Variables included within “Edaphic factors” are pH, clay
449 content (C), soil organic carbon (SOC), phosphorus content (P), soil bulk density (BD), and
450 microbial biomass (MB). Variables included within “Climatic factors” are monthly air
451 temperature (T) and monthly precipitation (P). Variables included within “Soil biodiversity”
452 are Acidobacteria (Aci), Actinobacteria (Act), Mortierellomycota (Mor), Verrucomicrobia
453 (Ver), Firmicutes (Fir), Nitrospirae (Nit), Chytridiomycota (Chy), Mucoromycota (Muc),
454 Ascomycota (Asc), Basidiomycota (Bas), Proteobacteria (Pro), N-fixing bacteria (Nfix),
455 Mycorrhiza (Myc), and plant pathogens (Pat). “PP” stands for primary productivity.

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